

Anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPA), at the heart of both rheumatoid arthritis and cardiovascular disease? The statistical analysis plan

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Abstract

Background: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a prevalent autoimmune disease leading to joint damage, disability, and increased mortality. Approximately 69% (95% confidence interval (CI) 39 to 94%) of patients with RA are positive for anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPA). ACPA are very specific for RA (specificity of 97% (range 81–100%)) and are seen as markers for underlying autoimmune pathophysiology. ACPA is detected in approximately 1% of healthy individuals. Most risk factors known for RA, such as smoking, or the presence of HLA shared epitope alleles are exclusively associated with autoantibody-positive disease. ACPA-positive RA patients have increased cardiovascular mortality. ACPA have been described in 10% of patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) without concomitant RA, a much higher prevalence than would be expected. Furthermore, ACPA were independently associated with poor cardiovascular outcomes and significantly increased mortality in these patients.

Objectives: To investigate the ACPA response in CHD by examining both the clinical phenotype of ACPA-positive CHD patients and the immunological characteristics of the ACPA in these patients (figure below). These findings will be compared to the existing data on the ACPA response in RA patients to gain more insight in the mechanisms underlying ACPA development and the specific ACPA features important in the pathophysiology of both diseases.

Part 1 ACPA in coronary heart disease

- How many and which patients with CHD are ACPA-positive? Can we replicate the findings that around 10% of patients with CHD without concomitant RA is ACPA-positive?

Part 2 Clinical phenotype, risk factors and disease outcomes

- Do ACPA-positive CHD patients differ from CHD-patients without ACPA regarding clinical phenotype and risk factors, such as female sex, smoking and low-grade inflammation?
- Do ACPA-positive CHD patients differ from CHD-patients without ACPA regarding disease outcomes, such as cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality?
- Is ACPA-positivity in CHD associated with the same risk factors and clinical outcomes as ACPA-positivity in RA?

Part 3 Immunological characteristics of ACPA

- What are the distinct immunological characteristics of ACPA in ACPA-positive CHD patients? We will focus on characteristics such as isotype usage, fine-specificity, avidity and glycosylation.

- B. Do the ACPA features in CHD differ from the ACPA features found in RA patients?
- C. Are certain ACPA features associated with clinical (CHD) outcomes, such as cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality, in patients with and without RA?

Schematic overview of an antibody with its different features

Methods

The specific patient populations and methods that will be used for each objective are stated in the table below. Stored samples and data from the following studies will be used: the clarithromycin for patients with stable coronary heart disease (CLARICOR) trial cohort containing CHD patients without RA ; the Leiden Early Arthritis Clinic (EAC) cohort containing RA patients ; and a cohort of healthy controls. The findings in the CLARICOR trial will be replicated in another CHD cohort: the LUDwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study . The flow of the analyses will be as following: First, we will determine the percentage of ACPA positive patients in the CLARICOR and LURIC studies. If the prevalence of ACPA is indeed increased in those patients compared to healthy donors, we will proceed with part 2 and 3.

Table 2	Topic	Populations		Methods
Part 1	Presence of ACPA in CHD (% of individuals positive)	CLARICOR and LURIC	Healthy population	Chi-square
Part 2A	Risk factors associated with ACPA-positivity in CHD	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-negatives in CLARICOR and LURIC	Univariate and multivariate logistic regression
Part 2B	Disease outcome in ACPA-positive compared to ACPA-negative CHD patients	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR (placebo group) and LURIC	ACPA-negatives in CLARICOR (placebo group) and LURIC	Univariate and multivariate (cause-specific) Cox regression
Part 2C	Compare risk factors/outcomes of ACPA-positivity in CHD and RA	CLARICOR and LURIC	Literature / EAC data	Use results of 2A and 2B, compare with literature / EAC data
Part 3A	ACPA characteristics in CHD	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC		Laboratory measurements
Part 3B	Compare ACPA features in CHD with ACPA features found in RA	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-positive EAC RA patients	T-test, Mann-Whitney U test, or chi-square
Part 3C	Association specific ACPA features and outcome in CHD and RA	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-positive EAC RA patients	Univariate and multivariate Cox regression

Discussion

ACPA are considered specific for rheumatoid arthritis. The findings that ACPA can also be present in patients with coronary heart disease offers a unique opportunity to learn more about pathophysiology of both diseases. With this study we aim to perform an investigation of the ACPA response in coronary heart disease (CHD) by examining both the clinical phenotype, risk factors and disease outcomes of ACPA-positive CHD patients and the immunological characteristics of the ACPA. By investigating whether ACPA-positivity in CHD is associated with the same risk factors, clinical outcomes and ACPA characteristics as ACPA in RA patients, we hope to gain more insight in the mechanisms underlying ACPA development and the specific ACPA features important in the pathophysiology of both diseases.

Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a prevalent autoimmune disease leading to joint damage, disability, and increased mortality. Cardiovascular comorbidities are a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in RA patients (1). Approximately two-thirds of patients with RA are positive for anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPA) (median 68.5%, range 39 to 94%) (2). ACPA is detected in approximately 1% of healthy individuals (3, 4), although this percentage can vary in smaller studies depending on the methods used. Citrulline is an enzymatic post-translational modification of the amino acid arginine. Citrullination is a physiological process and citrulline is present in all humans, yet for unknown reasons, immunological tolerance to citrulline is only lost in RA patients. ACPA are routinely determined in clinical practice since they are highly specific for RA (specificity of 97% (range 81 to 100%)) (2) and are part of the latest RA-classification criteria (4-6). ACPA may develop years before disease onset and are commonly seen as markers for underlying autoimmune pathophysiology (7). However, the pathophysiological processes causing the break of tolerance against citrullinated proteins, autoantibody expansion, and eventually arthritis remain largely unclear (7). Insights in these processes is of great importance as this could provide opportunities for earlier and better treatment options for RA patients.

ACPA, risk factors, and outcomes in RA

The most important risk factors for RA are smoking and the presence of certain HLA-DRB1 alleles: the so-called shared epitope (SE) alleles (8). Other factors associated with the risk of RA are for example female sex, obesity, low intake of omega-3 fatty acids, alcohol use and exposure to air pollution and silica dust (9-11). The discovery of ACPA has led to a paradigm shift in the ideas about RA development, because most risk factors known for RA are exclusively associated with autoantibody-positive disease (11, 12). Current concepts of RA pathophysiology therefore hypothesize that genetic and environmental risk factors lead to the development of ACPA, and that ACPA subsequently promote joint inflammation and thus RA (13).

The ACPA-positive and ACPA-negative RA subset differ not only regarding risk factors, but they are also associated with distinct disease outcomes. ACPA-positive RA patients have more joint destruction (14, 15). Moreover, ACPA-positive RA patients have increased cardiovascular mortality (16, 17).

ACPA characteristics in RA

ACPA and their specific characteristics (figure 1) have been extensively studied in RA patients.

Antibody characteristics, for example regarding isotype use and antigen-binding, reflect the underlying immunological processes (i.e. somatic hypermutation) and also determine the effector functions of the antibody (i.e. complement binding).

In RA, ACPA is often of the IgG isotype, but ACPA IgA and IgM can be present within a subset of ACPA-IgG positive patients, which may reflect an continuous ongoing immune response (18). ACPA are reactive against multiple citrullinated epitopes, which is called the fine-specificity of the ACPA response. A recent study suggests that reactivity against a large number of epitopes might be associated with an increased risk of

Figure 1: schematic overview of an antibody with its different features

cardiovascular disease in RA (19). ACPA can also be cross-reactive to other, structurally very similar post-translational modifications, being carbamylation (anti-carbamylated protein antibodies (anti-CarP)) and acetylation (anti-acetylated protein antibodies (AAPA)) (figure 2) (20). Another unique feature of ACPA is that they not only contain glycans in their constant region, but also in their variable domains. These variable domain glycans may play an important role in modulating antibody binding (21). The unique features of ACPA could reflect the specific processes underlying the development of autoimmunity in RA patients.

Figure 2: Cross-reactivity against post-translational modifications of proteins

Coronary heart disease and ACPA

There have been repeated observations of exaggerated and premature atherogenic processes amongst people with autoimmune disorders that lead to their increased morbidity and mortality (22). However, the underlying immunological mechanisms are not completely elucidated.

Intriguingly, ACPA have been described to occur in patients with coronary heart disease (CHD) without concomitant RA at a much higher prevalence than would be expected: 10.4% of patients with myocardial infarction compared to 3.8 % of controls (23). Using sera from the MISSION-study (consisting of patients with acute myocardial infarction), our group has replicated these data and found 10.5% of patients to be positive compared to 1.9% of healthy controls (figure 3) (24). None of these ACPA-positive patients developed RA after long-term follow-up. Additionally, we discovered that in these patients with CHD without RA, ACPA are independently associated with a poor cardiovascular outcome and significantly increased mortality (figure 4) (24).

Figure 3: ACPA-levels in patients with myocardial infarction without RA and healthy controls (28)

Research opportunities

These discoveries offer the unique opportunity to explore the development of anti-citrulline autoimmunity in completely different disease settings. The fact that ACPA can be detected years before disease onset in RA and in cardiovascular disease patients without RA suggests that not all ACPA immediately lead to arthritis. Investigating ACPA-positive patient subsets in these two diseases holds the promise of identifying unique associations between underlying risk factors, distinct autoantibody features, and the resulting disease phenotype. Insights into these associations could contribute to better understanding of the processes leading towards the break of tolerance against citrullinated proteins, the development of joint symptoms in RA, and the occurrence of CHD in ACPA-positive patients with and without RA. In conclusion, studying the ACPA response in CHD patients without RA and in ACPA-positive RA patients is an unprecedented opportunity to gain a better understanding of the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms in both CHD and RA.

Figure 4: Long-term re-infarction and all-cause mortality in ACPA-positive and ACPA-negative patients with myocardial infarction without RA (28)

Objectives

We aim to conduct an investigation of the ACPA response in CHD by examining both the clinical phenotype of ACPA-positive CHD patients and the immunological characteristics of the ACPA in these patients (figure 5). These findings will be compared to the existing data on the ACPA response in RA patients to gain more insight in the mechanisms underlying ACPA development and the specific ACPA features important in the pathophysiology of both diseases.

Figure 5: The aim of this research is to investigate risk factors, disease outcomes and ACPA characteristics within the ACPA-positive coronary heart disease patients and compare this to data found in RA.

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- Do the ACPA features in CHD differ from the ACPA features found in RA patients?
- Are certain ACPA features associated with clinical CHD outcomes, such as cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality, in patients with and without RA?

Patients and Methods

Populations

We will make use of several populations (table 1): the CLARithromycin for patients with stable CORonary heart disease (CLARICOR) trial cohort containing CHD patients where patients with a history of RA have been excluded (25); the Leiden Early Arthritis Clinic (EAC) cohort containing RA patients (26); and a cohort of healthy controls from Leiden. The findings will be replicated in another CHD cohort: the LUDwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study (27).

Table 1	Populations	
Part 1 ACPA in CHD	CLARICOR and LURIC	Healthy population
Part 2 Risk factors and outcomes	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-negatives in CLARICOR and LURIC
Part 3 Immunological characteristics of ACPA	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-positive EAC RA patients

Note: RA patients will be excluded from the CLARICOR beforehand, see below for details.

CLARICOR

The CLARICOR was a randomised, placebo-controlled multicentre trial including patients with a diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction (AMI) or angina pectoris (AP) living in Copenhagen between 1993 and 1999. Patients were randomised to clarithromycin versus placebo for a fortnight. In total 4373 patients were randomised — 2172 to the clarithromycin group and 2201 to the placebo group. Details have been published elsewhere (25). Demographic and anamnestic data, biochemical measurements at baseline and clinical information on the occurrence of cardiovascular outcomes between the start of the trial until 10-years follow-up are available for these patients (28). Genetic data and information on body mass index is not available. Diagnostic information on (co)morbidities is extracted from the Danish National Patient Register (NPR), which records a diagnosis using International Statistical Classification of Diseases (ICD) linked to each patient's Danish 10-digit central person registration, leading to a coverage of almost 100%.

Initially we will make use of random sample of 1000 patients that were included in the CLARICOR trial (500 from the clarithromycin group and 500 from the placebo group). To investigate the ACPA response in coronary heart disease (CHD) specifically, it is important that we exclude RA patients. This concerns not only the patients who had RA at inclusion, but also those who developed RA during follow-up, given that ACPA can be present years before RA development. To do so, we will exclude patients diagnosed with rheumatoid arthritis (rheumatoid factor positive and negative: ICD-10 codes M05, M06.0, M06.2-M06.9; ICD-8 codes 712.19, 712.39, 712.59) until the last moment of follow-up (December 31, 2009, at the latest). The 10-year follow-up of the CLARICOR trial should be sufficient to identify any patients that developed RA. Depending on the first results, it can be considered to measure a larger part of the CLARICOR than the initial ~1000 patients to identify more ACPA-positive CHD patients, which could be beneficial for the power of statistical analyses involving ACPA-positive CHD patients. For the analysis regarding disease outcome, it is preferable to include mainly patients from the placebo group due to the detrimental effects of clarithromycin (28).

LURIC

The LUDwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study is a German prospective cohort study comprised of individuals with and without CHD at baseline, based on coronary angiography.

3316 individuals are included in the LURIC between July 1997 and January 2000. Patients with “chronic polymorbid disease where non-cardiac disease predominates (i.e. severe rheumatic arthritis)” were excluded from the study. Details are described elsewhere (27). Information on the clinical parameters and biochemical measurements relevant for our study is available at baseline. Furthermore, cardiovascular events and deaths were recorded over a median observation period of 9.9 years. Another advantage is that this cohort includes a control group without CHD. However, there is limited data available on whether patients developed RA during follow-up.

EAC

The Leiden EAC is a population-based prospective cohort initiated in 1993 at the Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC) to detect and treat inflammatory disorders early in the disease state, especially early RA. Patients presenting with arthritis of less than 2 years symptom duration were included. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. The study was approved by the local medical ethics committee. At baseline, comorbidities and medication use were recorded, including cardiovascular disease. Definitive rheumatological diagnosis congruent with the presenting symptoms and their progression was made by a rheumatologist at one-year follow-up. For RA, diagnosis was made according to the 1987 EULAR/ACR Classification Criteria. Details are described elsewhere (26). In total this cohort contains more than 1200 consecutive RA patients and is still actively including more. All-cause mortality data is available for all patients, but because of regulatory changes in the Netherlands, information on cause of death for the EAC patients is readily available only until May 2008 (17). However, possibilities to gain access to cause of death data after May 2008 are investigated. Over the years, ACPA characteristics have been determined in a considerable subset of (ACPA-positive) RA patients in the EAC (18, 29-31), depending on inclusion date and availability of serum. If necessary, the ACPA profile can be determined in more EAC patients.

Healthy donors

Our cohort of healthy donors comprises of over 100 healthy individuals from the Leiden area aged between 20 and 70 years. Donors were recruited by campaigns in local newspapers, hospital flyers, and word-of-mouth. Candidates were included if they reported no major/chronic medical illnesses or joint complaints by questionnaire at inclusion.

All patient data and samples were collected in adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki (25-27, 32). Each cohort/trial was approved by the local medical ethics committee. All participants provided informed consent.

Laboratory measurements

Samples were obtained upon entry into the respective studies and stored at -80° C. The following measurements will be done per step:

Part 1 ACPA in coronary heart disease

- ACPA positivity and ACPA levels will be determined in all included CLARICOR and LURIC patients using commercial ACPA assays, using the cut-off as provided by the manufacturer.

Part 2 Clinical phenotype, risk factors and disease outcomes

- Data on ACPA positivity and levels obtained in part 1 will be used. No further laboratory measurements are required.

Part 3 Immunological characteristics of ACPA

Several distinct immunological characteristics of ACPA will be determined in ACPA-positive CHD patients. For a large part of ACPA-positive EAC patients, these data are already available from previous studies. If necessary, analyses of the ACPA-profile can be performed in more EAC patients. Standardised operating protocols for these methods have been developed and validated by the rheumatology laboratory department of the LUMC. Most of our in-house assays are based on the anti-CCP2 peptide, unless stated otherwise. The unmodified version of this peptide containing arginine instead of citrulline is taken along to ensure all observed signals are citrulline specific. Cut-offs are determined based on the mean plus 2 times the standard deviation of healthy controls. The following ACPA characteristics (figure 1, displayed again on the previous page) will be determined:

- The presence and levels of different ACPA isotypes by ELISA (IgG, IgA, IgM (18))
- The presence and levels of IgG directed against different citrullinated peptides and proteins by ELISA (so-called fine-specificity ELISAs (29))
- The avidity and affinity of the ACPA for citrullinated peptides and proteins by ELISA (31)
- The percentage of glycosylation of Fc- and Fab-region of purified ACPA by mass spectrometry (21)

Note: In case of a low number of ACPA-positive CHD patients or low ACPA levels in these patients, not all measurements may be technically feasible and useful. This will be considered per test.

Furthermore, also the presence and levels of other RA-associated autoantibodies that often co-occur in ACPA-positive RA patients will be determined by ELISA. This concerns rheumatoid factor IgM and antibodies against other posttranslational modifications, e.g. carbamylated proteins (anti-CarP) (30) and acetylated peptides (AAPA) (20). In figure 6, the overlap between RF IgM, anti-CCP2 IgG and anti-CarP IgG antibodies in the EAC is depicted.

Another test that can be considered is the detection of antibodies against malondialdehyde-acetaldehyde adducts (anti-MAA). These antibodies have been found in RA patients but are not specific for RA and can be found in other diseases (33). On the other hand, the presence of anti-MAA antibodies has been associated with coronary artery disease in patients without RA (34). This could thus be an interesting additional autoantibody to investigate in our studies. Depending on the results of currently ongoing studies in our department into the value of these antibodies in RA and other rheumatic diseases, measurements of anti-MAA will also be performed in CHD patients.

Statistical analyses

Before elaborating on the specific statistical analyses for each part of the study separately, there are some general principles applicable to all analyses. Normally distributed continuous variables will be

Figure 1: schematic overview of an antibody with its different features

Figure 6: Overlap RF IgM, anti-CCP2 IgG and anti-CarP IgG antibodies in EAC RA patients

reported as mean and standard deviation and compared with Welch's t-test (35). Skewed distributed continuous variables will be reported as median and interquartile range and compared with a Mann-Whitney U test (36). Categorical variables will be reported as number and percentage and compared with Pearson's chi-square test (37). Two-sided statistical tests with a significance level of 0.05 will be used. Of effect size statistics (described in the sections below), the point estimate with the 95% confidence interval (95% CI) and the p-value will be reported. For the analyses within each objective, we will also correct for multiple testing. The Holm-Bonferroni method will be used to assess whether p-values would still be considered significant ($\alpha=0.05$) after correction for multiple testing. Most laboratory tests used in this study provide information on both the presence as well as the levels of the autoantibodies/autoantibody features. Often, the presence of a particular autoantibody (feature) will be compared between groups. Within the patients that are positive for a certain autoantibody (feature), also the levels can be compared between both groups.

Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the analyses per research question. The analysis methods per research question are discussed in more detail below. The flow of the analyses is as follows: first we will determine in part 1 whether the prevalence of ACPA is significantly elevated in our CHD cohorts compared to healthy controls. We will also analyse this within the patient subset with the most severe CHD only, as this is more comparable to earlier studies (23, 24). If the prevalence of ACPA is indeed elevated in CHD patients, we will proceed to part 2 and 3. In case we cannot replicate earlier findings that ACPA is more present in CHD compared to healthy donors, it is not feasible to continue with part 2 and 3. Part 3 focusses on specific immunological characteristics of ACPA, for which multiple additional laboratory measurements of ACPA features are needed. Therefore, we plan to publish part 1-2 together first and part 3 in a separate publication afterwards.

Table 2	Topic	Populations		Methods
Part 1	Presence of ACPA in CHD (% of individuals positive)	CLARICOR and LURIC	Healthy population	Chi-square
Part 2A	Risk factors associated with ACPA-positivity in CHD	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-negatives in CLARICOR and LURIC	Univariate and multivariate logistic regression
Part 2B	Disease outcome in ACPA-positive compared to ACPA-negative CHD patients	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR (placebo group) and LURIC	ACPA-negatives in CLARICOR (placebo group) and LURIC	Univariate and multivariate (cause-specific) Cox regression
Part 2C	Compare risk factors/outcomes of ACPA-positivity in CHD and RA	CLARICOR and LURIC	Literature / EAC data	Use results of 2A and 2B, compare with literature / EAC data
Part 3A	ACPA characteristics in CHD	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC		Laboratory measurements
Part 3B	Compare ACPA features in CHD with ACPA features found in RA	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-positive EAC RA patients	T-test, Mann-Whitney U test, or chi-square
Part 3C	Association specific ACPA features and outcome in CHD and RA	ACPA-positives in CLARICOR and LURIC	ACPA-positive EAC RA patients	Univariate and multivariate Cox regression

Details analysis part 2 Clinical phenotype, risk factors and disease outcomes

- A. We will investigate which patient characteristics are associated with ACPA-positivity compared to non-positivity in patients with CHD. Our focus will be on factors associated with (ACPA-positive) RA, like age, female sex, BMI, smoking, pack years and markers of inflammation such as erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and C-reactive protein (CRP). If available, data on other environmental exposures, such as silica, and the presence of comorbidities such as chronic lung disease will also be investigated. Furthermore, lipid biomarkers will be investigated as omega-3 fatty acid intake has been suggested to inversely correlate with arthritis risk in ACPA-positive individuals by some, but not all studies (38-40). We will also look at serum-creatinine and glomerular filtration rate as higher levels of anti-carbamylated antibodies (which are potentially cross-reactive with citrulline) have been described in patients with kidney failure (41). When available, we will also investigate whether the main genetic risk factor for ACPA-positive RA, the presence of a so-called HLA shared epitope allele, is also associated with ACPA-positivity in CHD patients.

Univariate logistic regression will be used to investigate the risk factors for ACPA-positivity. The associations observed in univariate analyses might be affected by confounding factors. For example, BMI might be a confounder in the association between ESR and ACPA-positivity. Hence, for each potential risk factor that is investigated, factors that may confound that particular association will be taken into account. Multivariate logistic regression will be used after univariate analyses to correct for such possible confounders.

- B. The next question is whether ACPA-positivity is associated with a higher risk of worse clinical outcomes compared to ACPA-negativity in patients with CHD. The primary outcomes that will be investigated are a composite score of cardiovascular disease (comprising of myocardial infarction, unstable angina, cerebro-vascular disease, or cardiovascular death) and all-cause mortality. Furthermore, exploratory analyses into the separate components of the composite CVD score and non-cardiovascular death can be performed if the analyses into the primary outcomes provide significant results. For all-cause mortality, event-free survival will be analysed with Kaplan-Meier estimates and compared between groups with the log-rank test. For some outcomes, such as cardiovascular disease score, competing risks could be a problem. In case of the presence of competing risks, the cumulative incidence function will be used as it does not assume the independence of competing events. Analogous to the log-rank test for Kaplan-Meier estimates, Gray's test will be used to compare cumulative incidence functions between group. Cox proportional hazard models will be used to calculate hazard ratios, both univariate and with inclusion of possible confounders in the model. In case of competing risks, cause-specific hazards will be calculated using cox regression. The competing events will be treated as censored observations.

Known predictors of cardiovascular disease (42) may also be associated with ACPA-positivity in CHD patients, for example smoking. Variables that are associated with both ACPA-positivity and CHD clinical outcomes need to be taken along in the multivariate analysis to minimise confounding. Based on our findings in part 2A on risk factors for ACPA-positivity in CHD patients and what is known about risk factors for CHD and ACPA-positivity in literature, possible confounders will be selected and added to the multivariate model. Furthermore, we

need to take into account that clarithromycin had a negative effect on survival in the CLARICOR (28). Therefore, we will perform the main analysis in the placebo group only.

- C. The risk factors for ACPA in CHD analysed in 2A will be (qualitatively) compared to the known risk factors for ACPA-positivity in RA based on literature and previous publications in the EAC. Furthermore, the association of ACPA with CHD outcomes in RA, known from literature, previous publications in the EAC and if available also investigated in the full EAC data (including data after May 2008, using the methods described in 2B) will be compared to the associations found between ACPA and CHD outcomes in CHD non-RA patients in section 2B.

Details analysis part 3 Immunological characteristics of ACPA

- B. After the ACPA-features in CHD patients have been determined, these features will be compared to the ACPA characteristics found in RA patients.
- C. To investigate whether certain ACPA features are associated with clinical (CHD) outcomes we will use a similar approach as in part 2B.

Supplementary explorations

Previous analyses of ACPA in CHD patients have only been conducted in patients who suffered from myocardial infarction or who needed surgery for their CHD (23, 24). In CLARICOR, both patients with a history of myocardial infarction and patients with a history of angina pectoris are included. We will explore whether ACPA prevalence differs between these patient subsets, and whether stratification on this factor influences the conclusions drawn. Furthermore, it has been shown that clarithromycin had a negative effect on disease outcomes (28). Therefore, analyses regarding disease outcomes will be repeated after stratification for clarithromycin use.

Missing data

For the CLARICOR and the LURIC cohorts, missing data is expected to be minimal and to be missing completely at random (MCAR), as previously published (for placebo group only in CLARICOR) (27, 43). We will check this in both cohorts. A complete-case analysis will be done unless multiple imputation is necessary. For part 3 of the study, we will make use of the EAC cohort. Within the EAC, only the ACPA-positive RA patients will be used. For some analyses, the ACPA-positive EAC RA patient will be further selected based on availability of all-cause and cause-specific mortality data and on the availability of ACPA characteristics. There is no reason to assume that patients who were not measured for a certain ACPA characteristic differed in this characteristic compared to those who were measured, but additional measurements on the ACPA profile can be performed if necessary. So far, cause-specific mortality data is only available for EAC patients included before a certain date, as a result of a change in regulation regarding the extraction of data from national (cause of death) registries. This does not affect the association between ACPA characteristics and clinical outcomes. Therefore, a complete-case analysis will be done.

Replication study

In this study, we aim to perform an in-depth investigation of the ACPA response in coronary heart disease (CHD) by examining both the clinical phenotype of ACPA-positive CHD patients and the immunological characteristics of ACPA in these patients. We will use the LURIC study, an independent cohort of coronary heart disease patients, to try to replicate the observations found in the CLARICOR to increase the validity of our research.

Discussion

ACPA are very specific for rheumatoid arthritis. The findings that ACPA can also be present in patients with coronary heart disease (23, 24), offers a unique opportunity to learn more about pathophysiology of both diseases. In this study we aim to perform an investigation of the ACPA response in coronary heart disease (CHD) by examining both the clinical phenotype of ACPA-positive CHD patients and the immunological characteristics of the ACPA. By comparing these data to the existing data on the ACPA response in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients, we hope to gain more insight in the mechanisms underlying ACPA development and the specific ACPA features important in the pathophysiology of both diseases.

In this paper, we outline our rationale behind our research question and the approach we will take to answer these questions. Publishing a study protocol beforehand contributes to good research practises (44). Peer review is a valuable tool to improve study design already before the start of any measurements or analyses. Stating the research question and statistical analysis plan will restrict data dredging which can result in misleading results. Furthermore, selective reporting is prevented. Of course, it is possible that during the progress of this study new insights or unforeseen findings occur which ask for additional analyses (not specified in the current version of this plan). The authors will discuss whether it is indeed worthwhile and sensible to perform extra analyses or to deviate from this protocol in certain circumstances. If this is the case, we will provide the arguments for doing so and clearly state if an analysis was not specified beforehand.

Insights into the features of the autoimmune ACPA-response which are specifically seen in rheumatoid arthritis and not in CHD, may lead to a better understanding of how the ACPA response contributes to the development of joint symptoms and RA. This may provide new opportunities for the development of therapies aimed at targeting these specific mechanisms. If for example glycosylation of the Fab-region of ACPA is found to be specific for RA, therapeutic approaches aimed at modulating B-cell glycosylation mechanisms may prove to be effective. RA patients would benefit from better treatment options that can specifically target what goes awry in their (auto)immune response compared to the currently used more general immunosuppressive therapy with the associated risk of infections. Moreover, these therapies could already be used before actual disease develops, as it is known that the ACPA-response develops and matures before disease onset in RA (7). Identification of ACPA features associated with RA development could also lead to improved strategies for early recognitions of individuals at risk for RA. ACPA can for example be present in first-degree relatives of RA patients, but not all of these relatives will develop disease. Earlier recognition based on specific ACPA-characteristics would open doors to develop interventions to prevent the development of disease, an ultimate goal in RA research.

For CHD the knowledge gained from the proposed studies may result in a fundamental change of the pathophysiological disease concepts, in which autoimmunity may need to be incorporated. Consequently, immunosuppression could become a novel treatment option for a selection of CHD patient. Thus far, preliminary studies in CVD have been aimed at countering general inflammation. For example, the United States National Institutes of Health have funded the “Cardiovascular Inflammation Reduction Trial (CIRT)”; a randomized trial investigating whether low-dose methotrexate (an immunosuppressant commonly used in RA) can prevent recurrent cardiovascular events in high-risk patients (45). This illustrates that epidemiological data have already led to the notion that anti-rheumatic treatment may be beneficial in CVD. The present study would add

knowledge on the possible biological mechanisms behind these epidemiological observations. Furthermore, so far it seems that auto-immune associated processes may be particularly important in a certain subset of CHD patients. Identifying the patients that could potentially benefit most from anti-inflammatory treatment, would be a step forward in the development of more personalized treatment for CHD patients. Knowledge on the specific immunological aspects important for clinical outcome in CHD can help to identify specific treatment targets in these individuals. Thus, the same benefits concerning diagnosis, prognosis and treatment mentioned above for RA would apply as well for patients with CVD and individuals at risk. The figure of 10% ACPA-positive CVD patients may appear small at first glance but considering the extremely high population prevalence of this disease, the benefits to society could be substantial.

The CLARICOR trial is a study in which patients with stable CHD are included. This means that patients with the worst disease outcome, namely those who died from the first myocardial infarction, are not included in the CLARICOR cohort. Information about post-infarction heart failure and post-infarction angina pectoris was also not available. However, information about the medication at entry into CLARICOR could be used as a proxy. Furthermore, no genetic data is available in the CLARICOR cohort. This prohibits studies into the association between HLA shared epitope, a major risk factor for ACPA-positive RA, with ACPA-positivity in CHD patients. Another potential pitfall is that the CLARICOR cohort, the LURIC cohort, and the EAC cohort may differ in ways that we cannot measure. We cannot exclude that any differences in ACPA characteristics found are due to cohort differences. However, for this reason we plan to replicate our results in an independent cohort of CHD patients. This will increase the validity of our findings. For the CLARICOR patients, data are available on the development of RA during the years after inclusion, this data is lacking for the LURIC study. Therefore, some ACPA-positive LURIC patients could develop RA after inclusion. Furthermore, it is possible that some patients with RA may go on to develop CHD, making the distinction between features important for RA and CHD less clear. However, risk factors and clinical outcomes have been investigated in very large cohorts of ACPA-positive RA patients (at baseline). This increase the probability of finding a difference if it is present, even though there might be some RA-CHD patients in these cohorts.

This novel and innovative study is an outstanding collaboration across two different fields. The strength of this study is that we use data from two large, very well documented CHD cohorts in combination with in-depth methodology to study autoantibody responses. Using two independent CHD cohorts will contribute significantly to the validity of our findings. Other strengths of our study are the considerable size of the patient population and the long duration of follow-up. There are very few losses to follow-up and missing values are a rarity. A unique feature of the CLARICOR is the opportunity to very stringently exclude RA patients or those who go on to develop RA during the 10 years of follow-up.

In conclusion, with this study we hope to gain a better understanding of the role of ACPA in both coronary heart disease and rheumatoid arthritis by comparing patient characteristics, CHD outcomes and specific immunological characteristics of ACPA between CHD and RA patients.

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Statements

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Competing interests: None known.

Ethics: The LURIC study was in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the ethics committee at the Medical Association of Rheinland-Pfalz (Ärzttekammer Rheinland-Pfalz). The CLARICOR (NCT00121550) was approved by the Regional Ethics Committee (KF 01–076/99), the Danish Medicines Agency (2612–975) and the Danish Data Protection Agency (1999–1200–174). The EAC was conducted with the approval of the regional ethics committee at Leiden University Medical Center. All patients gave informed consent.

Data availability: Anonymized data will be provided upon reasonable request.

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